

TECHNICAL
REPORT OF
CARP BREEDING

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Introduction

Scientific classification

Domain: *Eukaryota*

Kingdom: *Animalia*

Phylum: *Chordata*

Class: *Actinopterygii*

Order: *Cypriniformes*

Family: *Cyprinidae*

Genus: *Cyprinus*

Species: *C. rubrofuscus*

Variety: *C. r. var. "koi"*

Ornamental carp breeding is an attractive and specialized aspect of aquaculture that revolves around the cultivation and improvement of carp species for aesthetic purposes. These fish, often characterized by their vibrant colors, distinct patterns, and graceful movements, hold immense appeal in the world of water parks, ponds, and aquariums. Ornamental carp breeding has evolved into an art form that combines biology, genetics and creative design.

One of the most famous ornamental carp species is the koi (*Cyprinus rubrofuscus*), which traces its origins to selective breeding of common carp. These beautiful fish display an impressive array of colors, from vibrant reds and oranges to soothing blues and whites. Each koi fish has a unique pattern, making them living canvases that fascinate enthusiasts and collectors around the world. Ornamental carp breeding involves a meticulous selection process that emphasizes specific traits such as color intensity, pattern clarity and body conformation. Breeders use genetic knowledge to achieve desired results, combining compatible parents to produce offspring with the most appealing traits. Over generations, this selective breeding leads to the refinement of traits, resulting in a diverse spectrum of koi varieties. The breeding process begins with the selection of mother fish with desired traits. These fish are then induced to spawn under controlled conditions, ensuring fertilization of the eggs. The fry, or young fish, are raised in special facilities with a focus on water quality, nutrition and disease prevention. This stage is critical because it determines the development of distinct colors and patterns that define ornamental carp.

Besides Koi, other ornamental carp species like Goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) are also of cultural and historical importance. These fish, with their amazing colors and different body shapes, have been admired by cultures around the world for centuries.

Breeding ornamental carp is not only about producing visually striking fish, but also about an appreciation of the natural world. Many enthusiasts take great pride in creating harmonious aquatic environments that showcase the beauty of these fish. Ponds and water gardens designed for ornamental carp often include elements such as aquatic plants, filtration systems and appropriate water circulation to mimic their natural habitat.

As technology advances, techniques such as genetic engineering and hybridization have added new dimensions to ornamental carp breeding. These innovations allow breeders to experiment to create new color variations and patterns, pushing the boundaries of what is achievable.

Varieties

Koi

Koi carp, scientifically known as *Cyprinus rubrofuscus*, are an ornamental fish that are selectively bred for their vibrant colors and unique patterns. Originating in Japan, these fish are highly prized for their aesthetic appeal and are often kept in outdoor ponds or water gardens. With centuries of history, koi carp have become symbols of beauty, longevity and good luck in many cultures. They come in different colors and patterns, each representing qualities and meanings. Koi carp are valued not only for their visual splendor but also for the tranquility they bring to the aquatic environment.

Kohaku

Kohaku is one of the most classic and beloved varieties of koi carp. Originating in Japan, this variety is recognized for its simple yet striking color combination of white body with dark red markings. The name "Kohaku" translates to "red and white" in Japanese, and captures the essence of the elegant and minimalist look of this variety. Kohaku carp are often considered the foundation of koi breeding and are highly sought after by enthusiasts for their beauty and symbolic significance.

Sanke carp

Another popular variety of koi, Sanke carp, is known for its attractive tri-color pattern. Originating in Japan, the Sanke variety features a white base with dark red and black markings. The name "Sanke" translates to "tricolor" in Japanese, reflecting the fish's unique combination of colors. The harmony between the white, red and black markings creates a visually appealing and balanced look. Sanke carp are highly regarded in the world of koi enthusiasts for their aesthetic charm and intricate patterns that make each fish unique.

Showa carp

The Showa carp is an attractive and colorful koi with a striking tricolor pattern. The Showa variety, which originated in Japan, features a black base with red and white markings. The combination of black, red and white creates a bold and dramatic contrast, making Showa carp an attractive addition to any pond or water garden. Named after Japan's Showa period, these koi are highly regarded for their intricate and complex patterns, often resembling beautiful works of art. Showa carp are prized by koi enthusiasts for their unique and eye-catching appearance, symbolizing both tradition and innovation in the world of ornamental fish.

Ogon carp

Originating in Japan, Ogon carp are a stunning and beautiful koi known for their unique metallic coloration. The name "ogon" translates to "golden" in Japanese, highlighting the shiny and reflective qualities of these fish. Ogon carp comes in a variety of metallic colors including gold, platinum and silver. Their simple yet attractive appearance is characterized by the absence of complex patterns or markings, allowing their bright color to take center stage. Ogon carp are prized for their understated beauty and the peaceful calm they bring to the aquatic environment, making them a popular choice among koi enthusiasts and pond keepers alike.

Anatomy of Carp Fish

Requirements for Breeding

Pond or tank

Provide a spacious and clean environment for spawning fish. A minimum size of 1,000 gallons or a pond with a dedicated breeding tank is ideal.

Water Quality

Maintain optimal water parameters including temperature (about 68-72°F or 20-22°C), pH (6.8-7.2), ammonia, nitrite and nitrate levels to ensure both health. . Mother fish and fry.

Adequate filtration

Use a reliable filtration system to keep the water clean and clear, as water quality greatly affects fish health and successful breeding.

Gender Identification

Learn to distinguish between male and female koi. Males typically have a slender body and small pointed pectoral fins, while females tend to be rounder with larger, more rounded pectoral fins. And the male pectoral fins are rough, Females pectoral fins are soft.

Selecting Parent Fish

Select healthy and mature koi with appropriate colors and patterns. Quality parent fish increase the likelihood of producing visually appealing offspring.

Seasonal Changes

To trigger spawning, mimic natural seasonal changes by gradually increasing the water temperature in the spring and decreasing it gradually in the fall. A temperature increase of about 5-7°F (3-4°C) over several weeks usually stimulates breeding.

Building substrate

Provide a suitable substrate, such as fine pea gravel or spawning mats, where the female can lay her eggs and the male can fertilize them.

Monitor Behavior

Observe fish for signs of spawning behavior such as chasing, luring, and vigorous swimming.

Egg Collection

Observe for eggs attached to substrate after hatching. If the parents are not removed, they may eat the eggs.

Fry Care

After the eggs hatch, the fry suck their yolk sacs. When they are free-swimming, start feeding them small, nutritious foods such as freshly hatched brine shrimp or commercial fry food.

Weaning and Growth

As chicks grow, they need more space and proper nutrition. Separate them into different tanks according to their size to prevent cannibals.

Remember, breeding koi requires knowledge, patience and dedication. It is advisable to gather information from reputable sources, attend workshops and connect with experienced breeders to improve your chances of success.

Carp Breeding Steps

01. Brood-stock Selecting

When selecting parents for breeding, look for fish in good health. Look for bold colors, distinct patterns, and good body conformation. It's crucial to choose fish that are free of illnesses and defects.

02. Conditioning

By feeding them a healthy, protein-rich diet, you can get the parent fish you've chosen ready for breeding. The fish should be in excellent health and reproductive condition after this conditioning phase, which helps to ensure that.

03. Creating a Breeding Environment

In a different pond or tank, create a conducive breeding environment. For the fish to lay their eggs on, the water should have some aquatic plants or other structures as well as be clean and well-aerated. This mimics the spawning conditions found in nature for koi, which are around 68–74°F (20–23°C).

04. Hormone Injection

Mother animals are the hormone Ovulin is used and injected in to male and female animals according to their weight. This is injected under the pectoral fin.

Male (1Kg) = 0.25 ml

Female (1Kg) = 0.5ml

05. Introduce the Fish to the tank

After the injection procedure the females introduce to the tank. After 6 hours the males introduce to the tank by 2:1 (male: female) ratio. The breeding pond or tank with the male and female fish. Keep a close eye on their behavior; the males might start chasing the females and the females might exhibit spawning-related behaviors like belly swelling.

06. Spawning Behavior

As egg scatters, koi fish discharge their eggs after 24 hours and sperm into the water, where external fertilization takes place. The female fish is typically chased by the male fish, who pokes her abdomen to cause the release of eggs. In order to fertilize the eggs in the water, the male then releases sperm.

07. Collection of eggs

You should keep an eye out for eggs in the water after spawning has taken place. Due to their adhesive nature, koi eggs will stick to objects like plants or pond machinery. If you have a separate breeding tank, you can return the parents to their natural habitat after collecting the eggs.

08. Incubation

Place the eggs that have been collected in an incubator or other system. To keep the eggs from sinking to the bottom, the water in this tank needs to flow slowly. To keep water quality high, use a sponge filter or a similar system. Within a few days, the eggs will hatch into fry.

09. Raising a fry

Since fries are delicate, particular care must be taken. Several times a day, feed them with powdered fish food or specialized fry food. Keep the water clean and keep the parameters in the right range. To avoid overcrowding as they grow, you might need to separate them into larger tanks.

10. Growing Up

The fry will require more space as they continue to grow. Move them into larger ponds or tanks gradually. The development of healthy growth and vibrant color depends on appropriate nutrition and routine water changes.

11. Selection and Elimination

Start spotting the fish with desirable characteristics as they get older. Fish with undesirable traits or deformities may need to be culled.

12. Patience

Patience and close observation are necessary for breeding and raising ornamental carp. Given the important role that genetics play in the development of color and pattern, it might take several generations to get the desired results.

Conclusion

Ornamental carp breeding exemplifies the integration of biology, aesthetics and human creativity. It serves as a testament to our fascination and beauty with the natural world and our desire to shape it in amazing ways. As enthusiasts and breeders continue to refine and expand the world of ornamental carp, they contribute to a living art form that enriches our lives and landscapes.

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